

TEACHER'S COMPETENCE-PRIORITY AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR LEARNING DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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Teacher's Competence-Priority and Teaching Performance: Basis for Learning Development Plan

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Abstract

Teachers' effectiveness is measured by how consistently they exhibit skills-related actions and how they apply their diverse abilities to accomplish tasks and achieve high-quality performance. Therefore, it is necessary to measure and determine the teachers' professional needs and priorities in order to provide adequate and effective professional growth and development. This study examined the capability, priorities, and teaching performance of secondary school teachers in selected high schools in the second district of Eastern Samar as input for a professional development plan. The study involved 287 high school teachers during the school year 2023-2024. Respondents answered survey questionnaires that solicited their demographic profiles, including teaching position, total years in teaching, educational attainment, and area of specialization. The findings revealed that among the 287 respondents, most held the position of Teacher II, had 4 to 7 years of teaching experience, most had earned master's units, and most specialized in TLE/TVL. The respondents demonstrated a moderate level of capability in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy ($\bar{x}=3.05$), learning environment ($\bar{x}=3.20$), curriculum, and planning ($\bar{x}=2.94$), as well as community linkages and professional engagement ($\bar{x}= 3.22$). Moreover, the 287 respondents indicated a high level of priority for development in content knowledge and pedagogy ($\bar{x}= 3.51$), while a low level of priority for development was noted in learning environment ($\bar{x}=1.96$), curriculum and planning ($\bar{x}=2.16$), as well as community linkages and professional engagement ($\bar{x}= 1.89$). Based on the results, a highly significant relationship was found between the respondents' level of capability and their teaching performance ($r= .439$, $p\text{-value} = .000$). Furthermore, a highly significant relationship was also found between the respondents' level of priority for development and their teaching performance ($r= .373$, $p\text{-value}= .000$). Among the respondents' profiles, teaching position ($r= .206$, $p\text{-value} = .002$), total years in teaching ($r= .170$, $p\text{-value} = .040$), and educational attainment ($r= .185$, $p\text{-value} = 0.44$) were found to be significantly related to teaching performance, while area of specialization showed no significant relationship. This study recommends that teachers aim to upgrade their teaching positions, either through promotion or reclassification, by fulfilling the basic requirements in accordance with DepEd policies and guidelines, as teaching position was found to be a significant contributing factor to teaching performance. Teachers should also strive to pursue higher education to update their professional skills and learn about contemporary trends in the educational system.

Keywords: *competence, learning development, learning environment, performance, professional engagement*

Introduction

In light of today's world's changing demands and challenges, expectations for teacher quality in the Philippines have undergone significant transformation. Present reforms call for teachers to critically re-evaluate their roles and responsibilities within the framework of the K-12 education system. Even though the Department of Education wishes to keep supporting teachers' professional development without wavering, we must look at its main issue and take immediate action to address it to move the Philippine educational system toward productivity. Research shows that effective professional development must be tailored to each learner's specific needs and circumstances, as Broad and Evans (2006) stated. Broad and Evans (2006) went on to state that sustained, continuous, in-depth professional development necessitates the active participation of the professional. Short-term, "pull-out," "one-shot," and similar programs are thought to be ineffectual in advancing or altering practice.

In the context of the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) is dedicated to giving its employees the chance to connect their accomplishments with the institution's vision and mission, foster team and individual development, engagement, and commitment, and advance both professionally and personally (DepEd, 2019 cited in Cruzos, 2022). Aligned with this philosophy, the Department of Education (DepEd) has introduced a Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). This system fosters collaboration between managers and employees, promoting open discussions about responsibilities, goals, and Key Results Areas (KRAs) and their alignment with the department's broader objectives. It acts as a framework for establishing performance and conduct standards within the organization, fostering improvements in both personal and professional growth (Cruzos, 2022).

A teacher's effectiveness is measured by how consistently they exhibit skills-related actions and by how they apply their diverse abilities to accomplish tasks and achieve high-quality performance. Teachers are held accountable for their work attitudes and teaching performance. The secretary of the Department of Education emphasized that the Philippines' current educational crisis is putting the nation at the bottom of the scale in terms of context for literacy and numeracy. To provide adequate and effective professional growth and development, it is therefore necessary to measure and determine the professional needs and priorities of the teachers.

Research Questions

This research aimed to investigate the capabilities, priorities, and teaching performance of secondary school teachers in selected high

schools within the Second District of Eastern Samar, Philippines. This specifically aimed to respond to the following queries:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. position;
 - 1.2. total number of years in teaching;
 - 1.3. educational attainment; and
 - 1.4. area of specialization?
2. What is the level of capability and priority for development of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 2.2. learning environment;
 - 2.3. curriculum and planning; and
 - 2.4. community linkages and professional engagement?
3. What is the teaching performance of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of capability, priority for development, and teaching performance of the respondents?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the teaching performance of the respondents?

Literature Review

According to Shulman's (2021) reasoning, in order for teachers to successfully and productively instruct, they require seven knowledge bases. The knowledge bases encompass content knowledge, general pedagogical knowledge, curriculum knowledge, understanding of learner characteristics, awareness of educational contexts, and knowledge of educational goals, purposes, and values, including their philosophical and historical foundations. Conversely, Grossman (2020) contended that a teacher only needs to have three knowledge bases to effectively teach: subject matter, school contexts, and pedagogy. According to Barnett and Hodson (2021), excellent teachers employ four different types of knowledge in their instruction: professional knowledge, academic and research knowledge, content knowledge and pedagogy, and classroom knowledge. Although scholars hold differing views on the knowledge bases required for educators, they generally agree on several key areas, particularly subject matter and pedagogy—specifically, content knowledge and pedagogical skills—which are crucial predictors of an effective and efficient teaching environment.

Understanding fundamental concepts like knowledge, the teaching and learning process, and how teachers apply their knowledge in the classroom are all necessary to conceptualize teacher knowledge, which is a challenging task (Olfos, 2019). Furthermore, as Tesfay (2020) emphasizes, empirical research demonstrates that teacher quality plays a significant role in determining increases in students' academic achievement. The findings of current research on the educational production function may be constrained by insufficient explanations of teachers' knowledge. This includes limitations in terms of the extent to which teachers' knowledge affects students' learning as well as the specific types of knowledge that are most important in achieving students' learning objectives (Stofile, 2017).

Smith and Neale (2023) held a similar opinion, believing that educators who possess strong pedagogical content knowledge are aware of the common mistakes that students make when studying a given subject. Consequently, they can design their lessons using suitable techniques and elaboration that facilitate students' understanding of concepts. According to Cochran et al. (2021), content knowledge also includes how teachers connect their pedagogical knowledge—what they know about teaching—with their subject matter knowledge, or what they know about what they teach, and how subject matter knowledge fits into the process of pedagogical reasoning.

Effective teaching and learning strategies, sufficient teaching resources, a welcoming classroom atmosphere, a positive school culture, child-centered education, impartial administration, and sufficient school physical infrastructures were all necessary for a productive school environment (Philip & Lagos, 2021). Flower and Melbery (2009) found that most schools are not in the best locations, and the atmosphere is not favorable for learning.

According to Caprara et al. (2023), classroom design has an effect on teachers' emotions and sense of preparedness for a profession that has grown more demanding and significant in recent years, in addition to its effects on students. According to Klassen and Tze (2023), a number of studies have shown how the physical learning environment affects teachers' sense of efficacy as determined by the Teacher Sense of Efficacy Scale. Among other things, self-efficacy is linked to higher teaching effectiveness and better academic achievement. To put it simply, when educators feel they can effectively instruct students, they behave accordingly.

Moreover, according to Shield and Dockrell (2021), internal factors like the kind of activity being done in the classroom, the number of students, and so on largely determined the noise levels in the classroom. These levels were not significantly impacted by outside noise levels. It should be noted, however, that when the children were reading quietly, outside noises were more significant—and possibly distracting—than when the classroom windows were closed. However, they discovered that background noise in vacant classrooms was louder than recommended.

Furthermore, a thoughtfully designed curriculum not only creates a meaningful and engaging learning environment but also clarifies expectations for students in the classroom. An effective curriculum provides teachers, students, administrators, and community members with a measurable framework for delivering high-quality instruction.

Scherz (2021) asserted that professional engagement—a frequently disregarded aspect of professional learning, or PD—is essential for educators to progress in their careers. Professional learning must include the application of theory, skill mastery, and refreshers on foundational knowledge; however, if engagement is low, these components will be less effective. Additionally, the basis of this perspective is professional engagement as a result of an individual's intrinsic motivation or organic commitment to their work; however, it is important to consider three planes of resistance (Kahn, 1990). Personal obstacles will reduce a teacher's commitment to their work on a single level. Systemic factors, like ties to the administration and the division between labor unions and school leadership, can also act as obstacles. The last group of obstacles comes from cultural factors like local, state, and federal laws (Lockwood, 2007).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. It looked at the respondents' positions, years of total teaching experience, level of education, and area of specialization. According to Worth (2008) as cited in Cruzos (2022) a descriptive research design is a scientific approach that entails observing and characterizing a subject's behavior without exerting any kind of influence on it. Additionally, it aimed to investigate the relationship between teachers' capabilities and priorities regarding content knowledge, pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum, planning, community connections, professional engagement, and teaching performance.

Respondents

This study was carried out in various secondary schools within the second district of Eastern Samar. The participants in the study consisted of secondary school teachers ranging from Teacher I to Teacher III at the selected high schools in the second district of Eastern Samar. A total of two hundred eighty-seven (287) high school teachers from Teacher I to Teacher III took part in this study. The researcher carried out a pre-survey to verify the total number of samples from the different schools, which provided a scientific basis for selecting study respondents. To streamline the process of selecting study samples, the researcher utilized stratified random sampling, a probability sampling technique commonly used in sample surveys.

Instrument

A survey questionnaire was used in the study to address specific issues. The questionnaire is divided into three sections. Part I provides the demographic profile of the respondents, including details about their position, total years of teaching experience, level of education, and area of specialization. Part II contains sub-sections of the Results-Based Performance Management System-Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers Self-Assessment Tool for Proficient Teachers (Teachers I to III), which relate to the levels of capability and priority areas for development, including content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, community links, and professional engagement, as outlined in the Annex of DepEd Order No. 2. Revisions to DepEd Order No. 004 were made in 2022. Using a 5-point Likert scale, the ratings were as follows: 1 represented very low, 2 represented low, 3 represented moderate, 4 represented high, and 5 represented very high. Part III assesses the teaching performance of the respondents using the most recent Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) rating. This variable was evaluated according to the IPCR scoring guidelines for teachers (Cruzos, 2022).

Procedure

The principals of the participating schools, along with the superintendent of the school division, granted the researcher permission prior to distributing the questionnaire. After receiving the necessary clearance, the researcher personally delivered the survey questionnaire to each respondent at their respective schools to ensure 100% retrieval. Additionally, using the implemented strategy, the researcher addressed any questions raised by the respondents. This study was carried out during June and July 2024.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the respondents was compiled and analyzed. Means, frequency counts, and percentages were employed to assess and understand the respondents' demographic profile, levels of capability, priority areas for development, and teaching performance. The relationship between the independent and dependent variables was analyzed using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient, conducted at a 5% level of significance.

Ethical Considerations

Furthermore, the researchers explained to the respondents the objectives as well as the problem posed by the study. To ensure the safety and rights of the possible participants, informed consent, voluntary participation, rights of participants, anonymity, and confidentiality were considered (Chigona et al., 2010).

Results and Discussion

The data presented in this section reflects the capabilities, priorities, and teaching performance of secondary school teachers from the selected high schools in the second district of Eastern Samar. Tabular presentations illustrate the frequency counts and percentages of the respondents' profiles, depicting the relationships between the different variables of the study.

Demographic Profile of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar

The tables below provide a detailed overview of the respondents' demographic profile.

Position. Table 1 shows the respondents' profiles in terms of teaching positions. As indicated in the table, there were 102 (35.50 percent) Teacher I, 112 (39.00 percent) Teacher II, and 73 (25.40 percent) Teacher III.

Table 1. *The Teaching Position of the Respondents*

<i>Teaching Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Teacher I	102	35.50
Teacher II	112	39.00
Teacher III	73	25.40
Total	287	100.00

Teachers in higher positions or those with additional responsibilities often have greater access to professional development opportunities, which can improve their teaching skills and performance. This suggests that a teacher's position can influence their growth and effectiveness in the classroom.

Total Number of Years in Teaching. Table 2 depicts the profile of the respondents in terms of total number of years in teaching. Based from the table, 36 or 12.50 percent has more than 12 years teaching experience, while 72 or 25.10 percent 8 to 11 years teaching experience, 120 or 41.80 percent with 4 to 7 years ad 59 or 20.60 percent has 0 to 3 years teaching experience.

Table 2. *The Total Number of Years in Teaching of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar*

<i>Total Number of Years in Teaching</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
More than 12 Years	36	12.50
8 to 11 years	72	25.10
4 to 7 years	120	41.80
0 to 3 years	59	20.60
Total	287	100.00

Based on the presented data, the majority secondary school teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar have 4 to 7 years of teaching experience.

Educational Attainment. Table 3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their educational attainment. As shown in the table, there were 2 or 0.70 percent doctorate degree, 5 or 1.70 percent with doctorate degree, 47 or 16.40 percent master's degree, 158 or 55.10 percent with master's unit, and 75 or 26.10 percent bachelor's degree.

Table 3. *The Educational Attainment of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Doctorate Degree	2	0.70
With Doctorate Unit	5	1.70
Master's Degree	47	16.40
With Master's Unit	158	55.10
Bachelor's Degree	75	26.10
Total	287	100.00

The table shows that the majority of secondary school teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar have completed master's units.

Area of Specialization. Table 4 presents the respondents' profiles according to their areas of specialization. It indicates that 45 respondents, or 15.70 percent, specialized in English; 32, or 11.10 percent, were Filipino majors; 41, or 14.30 percent, were Mathematics majors; 34, or 11.80 percent, specialized in Science; 50, or 17.40 percent, were Social Science majors; 1, or 0.30 percent, was a Values Education major; 15, or 5.20 percent, were MAPEH majors; 63, or 22.00 percent, specialized in TLE/TVL; and 6, or 2.10 percent, focused on other fields.

Table 4. *The Area of Specialization of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar*

<i>Area of Specialization</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
English	45	15.70
Filipino	32	11.10
Mathematics	41	14.30
Science	34	11.80
Social Science	50	17.40
Values Education	1	0.30
MAPEH	15	5.20

TLE/TVL	63	22.00
Others	6	2.10
Total	287	100.00

According to the data presented, the majority of Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar specialized in TLE/TVL subjects

Level of Capability of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar

The tables below demonstrate the level of capability among Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar.

Table 5. *Summary on the Level of Capability of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.05	Moderate
Learning Environment	3.20	Moderate
Curriculum and Planning	2.94	Moderate
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.22	Moderate
Grand Mean	3.10	Moderate

Based on the result presented, a grand mean of 3.10 implies that the Level of Capability of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar is moderate. As shown in the table, in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, the respondents exhibit a moderate level of capability (\bar{x} - 3.05). Moreover, the learning environment is at a moderate level with a mean of 3.20. The table also indicates a mean of 2.94, suggesting that the level of capability of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar regarding curriculum and planning is at a moderate level. And lastly, the table reveals a mean of 3.22, indicating that the Level of Capability of Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar regarding Community Linkages and Professional Engagement is at a moderate level.

According to the study of Suglo et al. (2023), found a significant relationship between the independent variable teacher's pedagogical content knowledge and the dependent variable academic performance in the circle theorem signifying that students' performance in the circles theorem depends on the pedagogical content knowledge of the teacher. According to Sittar (2020), the results of the study demonstrated that professional engagement improved teachers' capacity to perform their duties. Therefore, it is suggested that in order for teachers to properly fulfill their duties in a classroom setting, they should be professionally engaged in their work.

Level of Priority for Development of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar

The following tables illustrate the Level of Priority for Development of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar.

Table 6. *Summary on the Level of Priority of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar*

Level of Priority for Development	Grand Mean	Interpretation
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.51	High
Learning Environment	1.96	Low
Curriculum and Planning	2.16	Low
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	1.89	Low
Total Grand Mean	3.10	Low

As presented in the table, the content knowledge and pedagogy got a mean of 3.51, implying that the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar prioritize its development. The table shows a grand mean of 1.96, indicating that the learning environment for Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar is viewed as a low priority for development. Based on the presented data, a grand mean of 2.16 suggests that curriculum and planning among Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar is considered a low level of priority for development. Based on the presented data, a grand mean of 1.89 implies that the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement is low level of priority for development.

According to Tesfay (2020), empirical research shows that teacher quality is an important factor in determining gains in students' achievement. By inadequately explaining teachers' knowledge, existing educational production function research could be limited in its conclusions, not only by the magnitude of effects that teachers' knowledge has on students' learning but also about the kinds of teacher knowledge that matters most in producing students' learning outcomes (Stofile, 2017). As affirmed by DepEd (2020), teachers play a role in establishing school-community partnerships aimed at enriching the learning environment and engaging the community in the educative process.

Teaching Performance of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar

Table 7 presents the teaching performance of Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar. According to the

data, 66 respondents, representing 10.50 percent, were rated as outstanding, 191 respondents or 66.60 percent were rated as very satisfactory, and 30 respondents or 23 percent were rated as satisfactory.

Table 7. *Teaching Performance of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar*

Teaching Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	66	23.00
Very Satisfactory	191	66.60
Satisfactory	30	10.50
Total	287	100.00

The results indicate that the majority of Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar demonstrated very satisfactory teaching performance.

Relationship Between the Level of Capability, Priority for Development, and Teaching Performance of the respondents

Table 8 presents the relationship between the level of capability, development priorities, and teaching performance of secondary school teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar. The table reveals a correlation coefficient of .439, indicating a moderate correlation, with $p < .05$, suggesting a highly significant relationship between teachers' capability levels and their teaching performance. This implies that teachers' capabilities in areas such as content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, and community linkages and professional engagement are important factors that contribute to improved teaching performance. As shown in Table 8, the teachers were rated as very satisfactory in teaching performance, despite having only a moderate level of capability across all performance indicators.

Table 8. *Relationship Between the Level of Capability, Priority for Development and Teaching Performance of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar*

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Capability	Teaching Performance	.439	Moderate Correlation	.000	Highly Significant
Priority for Development	Teaching Performance	.373	Low Correlation	.000	Highly Significant

Additionally, Table 8 highlights the relationship between development priorities and teaching performance. The table shows a correlation coefficient of .373, indicating a low correlation, with $p < .05$, signifying a highly significant relationship between development priorities and teaching performance. This suggests that the focus on teachers' development should be considered, as it impacts how effectively they carry out their duties and responsibilities.

Relationship Between the Demographic Profile and Teaching Performance of the Respondents

Table 9 presents the relationship between teaching position and teaching performance. The table shows a correlation coefficient of .206, interpreted as a low correlation, with $p < .05$, indicating a significant relationship between these two variables. This suggests that a teacher's current position may influence their performance, and it could also imply that teachers who remain in the same position for an extended period may lack motivation to excel in their duties.

In addition, Table 9 reveals a correlation coefficient of .170, interpreted as a negligible correlation, with $p < .05$, indicating a significant relationship between years of teaching experience and performance. This suggests that teaching performance is influenced by the length of a teacher's experience.

Furthermore, the table shows a correlation coefficient of .185, also interpreted as a negligible correlation, with $p < .044$, indicating a significant relationship between educational attainment and teaching performance. This implies that teachers with higher levels of education are more likely to perform better in their teaching roles.

Table 9. *Relationship Between the Demographic Profile and Teaching Performance of the Secondary School Teachers in the Second District of Eastern Samar*

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation
Teaching Position	Teaching Performance	.206	Low Correlation	.002	Significant
Total Number of Years in Teaching		.170	Negligible Correlation	.040	Significant
Educational Attainment		.185	Negligible Correlation	.044	Significant
Area of Specialization		.173	Negligible Correlation	.384	Not Significant

Conversely, no significant relationship was found between the respondents' area of specialization and their teaching performance, as indicated by a correlation coefficient of .173, interpreted as a negligible correlation with $p > .05$. This aligns with Desimone's (2009)

study, Improving Impact Studies of Teacher's Professional Development: Toward Better Conceptualizations and Measures, which highlights the significant role demographic factors play in determining teaching performance. When these factors are effectively aligned and integrated, they contribute to enhanced teacher effectiveness and better student outcomes.

Conclusions

The study's findings revealed that the respondents' teaching performance was significantly impacted by their level of capability and development priorities, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which posited no meaningful correlation between teaching performance and either skill level or development priority. The results suggest that the teachers' growth and abilities are critical factors in their instructional performance, with how the administration and individuals addressed their needs playing a vital role in how they fulfilled their teaching responsibilities.

Additionally, a significant relationship was also identified between teaching performance and the respondents' teaching position, years of experience, and educational attainment. Taking into consideration the previously mentioned outcomes, conclusions, and recommendations, the researcher subsequently suggests:

The study's findings indicate that teachers still need both professional and personal development to enhance their competence. Furthermore, since teaching position was identified as a significant factor influencing teachers' performance, it is essential for teachers to seek to upgrade their position, which may involve pursuing a promotion or reclassification, by reviewing the basic requirements set forth by DepEd policies and guidelines.

In addition, educators ought to make an effort to continue their education in order to stay up to date on new developments in the field, learn about cutting edge practices in the classroom, and support their students in engaging in activities that will help them reach their full potential.

The principal of the school must keep assisting teachers in their professional development. School leaders are among the first to recognize the importance of teachers' roles and responsibilities, so they should be a good source of encouragement and motivation to keep teachers with high levels of competence and a positive attitude.

Understanding that teachers need more than just intellectual professional development, master teachers and head teachers should provide their subordinates with high-quality, timely technical assistance. Furthermore, the Learning Action Cell (LAC) and other school-based professional development seminars and training sessions will be extensively implemented and monitored, allowing teachers to enhance their skills and effectively apply them in the classroom.

It is strongly recommended that the intervention plan be implemented and monitored extensively to ensure that teachers receive the professional and personal development essential for fulfilling their roles as educators. Additionally, further relevant research is highly recommended to corroborate the study's diverse conclusions.

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